

A Novel Approach to Allow Process into Critical Section with no delay-time

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Abstract

This paper proposes a new idea which makes the processes not to wait for a long time to enter into a critical section to access a data structure which is already assigned to the other process and that process enters into critical section. Till date so many approaches and algorithms are proposed to reduce the delay time between the successive executions of the critical section, but no one proposed how to assign the data structure to all the process who are requesting for the data structure. In this paper the idea we are proposing is to create an instance of the data structure before assigning to the process and allow each and every process into critical section to avoid the delay time permanently. The proposed algorithm every time creates an instance of the data structure before assigning to the requested process and simultaneously it checks for the instance released by the process already assigned instanced data structure. If when a new process is requesting for the data structure and at the same time already assigned process releases the instance then the coordinator will do both creation and deletion of the instance.

Keywords

Mutual Exclusion, Critical Section, Resource management, group mutual exclusion.

I. Introduction

MUTUAL exclusion is one of the most fundamental problems in concurrent systems including distributed systems. In this problem, access to a shared resource (that is, execution of critical section) by different processes must be synchronized to ensure its integrity by allowing at most one process to access the resource at a time. The concept of time is fundamental to our way of thinking. It is derived from the more basic concept of the order in which events occur. We say that something happened at 10:20 if it occurred after our clock read 10:20 and before it read 10:21 [2]. A distributed system consists of a collection of distinct processes which are spatially separated, and which communicate with one another by exchanging messages. A network of interconnected computers such as the ARPA net, is a distributed system. A single computer can also be viewed as a distributed system in which the central control unit, the memory units, and the input-output channels are separate processes. A system is distributed if the message transmission delay in is not negligible compared to the time between events in a single process. Numerous solutions and extensions have been proposed to the basic mutual exclusion problem. More recently, another extension to the basic mutual exclusion problem, called group mutual exclusion (GME), has been proposed [7]. The group mutual exclusion problem extends the traditional mutual exclusion problem by associating a type (or a group) with each critical section. In this problem, processes requesting critical sections of the same type can execute their critical sections concurrently. However, processes requesting critical sections of different types must execute their critical sections in a mutually

exclusive manner [1].

In distributed systems, many applications, such as replicated data management, directory management, and distributed shared memory, requires that a shared resource is allocated to a single process at a time. This is called the problem of mutual exclusion. The problem of mutual exclusion becomes much more complex in distributed systems (as compared to single-computer systems) due to the lack of both a shared memory and a common physical clock and because of unpredictable message delays.

Since a shared resource is expensive and processes that cannot get the shared resource must wait, the performance of mutual exclusion algorithms is critical to the design of high-performance distributed systems. The performance of mutual exclusion algorithms is generally measured by message complexity and synchronization delay. The message complexity is measured in terms of the number of messages exchanged per Critical Section (CS) execution. The synchronization delay is the time required after a site exits the CS and before the next site enters the CS and it is measured in terms of the average message delay T [8]

Distributed mutual exclusion algorithms are either token-based or nontoken-based. In token-based mutual exclusion algorithms, a unique token exists in the system and only the holder of the token can access the protected resource. Examples of token-based mutual exclusion algorithms are Suzuki-Kasami's algorithm [4] (N messages), Singhal's heuristic algorithm [9] ($\lceil N/2, N \rceil$ messages), Raymond's tree-based algorithm [5] ($\log(N)$ messages), Yan et al.'s algorithm [10] ($O(N)$ messages), and Naimi et al.'s algorithm [11] ($O(\log(N))$ messages). Nontoken-based mutual exclusion algorithms exchange messages to determine which process can access the CS next. Examples of nontoken-based mutual exclusion algorithms are Lamport's algorithm [2] $3(N-1)$ messages), Ricart-Agrawala's algorithm [3] $2(N-1)$ (messages), Carvalho-Roucairol's variant of the Ricart-Agrawala algorithm [12] ($[0, 2(N-1)]$ messages), Maekawa's algorithm [13] ($\beta \sqrt{N} \sqrt{N}$ messages), and Singhal's dynamic information structure algorithm [14] ($[N-1, 3(N-1)/2]$ messages). Sanders gave a theory of information structures to design mutual exclusion algorithms, where an information structure describes which processes maintain information about what other processes, and from which processes a process must request information before entering the CS [15].

Due to the absence of global time in a distributed system, timestamps are assigned to messages according to Lamport's clocks [2].

II. Related Work

In this section, we describe the general system model and review few algorithms which are best known fair distributed mutual exclusion algorithms. The algorithm proposed in Section III is an improvement over the following algorithms.

A. System Model

The RA algorithm and the algorithm by Lamport assume the following model. There are N processes in the system.

The processes communicate only by asynchronous message passing over an underlying communication network which is error-free and over which message transit times may vary. Processes are assumed to operate correctly. Unlike the RA algorithm but similar to Lamport's algorithm, we assume FIFO channels in the communication network. Without loss of generality, we assume that a single process executes at a site or a node in the network system graph. Hence, the terms process, site, and node are interchangeably used.

A process requests a CS by sending REQUEST messages and waits for appropriate replies before entering its CS. While a process is waiting to enter its CS, it cannot make another request to enter another CS. Each REQUEST for CS access is assigned a priority and REQUESTs for CS access should be granted in order of decreasing priority for fair mutual exclusion. The priority or identifier, ReqID, of a request is defined as $\text{ReqID} = (\text{SequenceNumber}, \text{PID})$, where SequenceNumber is a unique locally assigned sequencenumber to the request and PID is the process identifier. SequenceNumber is determined as follows. Each process maintains the highest sequence number seen so far in a local variable Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen. When a process makes a request, it uses a sequence number which is one more than the value of Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen. When a REQUEST is received, Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen is updated as follows:

$$\text{Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen} \\ = \text{maximum}(\text{Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen}, \\ \text{sequence number in the REQUEST})$$

Priorities of two REQUESTs, ReqID_1 and ReqID_2 , where $\text{ReqID}_1 = (\text{SN}_1, \text{PID}_1)$ and $\text{ReqID}_2 = (\text{SN}_2, \text{PID}_2)$, are compared as follows. Priority of ReqID_1 is greater than priority of ReqID_2 iff $\text{SN}_1 < \text{SN}_2$ or $(\text{SN}_1 = \text{SN}_2 \text{ and } \text{PID}_1 < \text{PID}_2)$. All REQUESTs are thus totally ordered by priority. This scheme implements a variant of Lamport's clock mentioned in introduction, and when requests are satisfied in the order of decreasing priority, fairness is seen to be achieved.

B. Ricart-Agrawala Algorithm

The algorithm uses two types of messages: REQUEST and REPLY [16].

1. Variables for process P_i

Each process P_i uses the following local integer variables:

- (I) seq_Number i ,
- (II) ReplyCount and
- (III) Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen i ,
- (IV) P_i also uses the following vector:
RD $_i[1:N]$ of Boolean. RD $_i[j]$ indicates if P_i has deferred the REQUEST sent by P_j .

2. Algorithm

The RA algorithm is outlined in Fig. 1. Each procedure in the algorithm is executed atomically. The REPLY messages sent by a process are blocked only by processes that are requesting the CS with higher priority. Thus, when a process sends REPLY messages to all deferred requests, the process with the next highest priority request receives the last needed REPLY

message and enters the CS. The execution of CS requests in this algorithm is always in the order of their decreasing priority. For each CS access, there are exactly $2(N - 1)$ messages: $(N - 1)$ REQUESTs and $(N - 1)$ REPLYs.

3. Classification

(I) Requesting Site

It sends a message to all web sites. This message includes the site's name, and the current timestamp of the system according to its logical clock (which is assumed to be synchronized with the other sites).

(II) Receiving Site

- Upon reception of a request message, immediately send a time stamped reply message if and only if:
 1. the receiving process is not currently interested in the critical section
 - OR
 2. the receiving process has a lower priority (usually this means having a later timestamp)
- Otherwise, the receiving process will defer the reply message. This means that a reply will be sent only after the receiving process has finished using the critical section itself.

(III) Critical Section

- Requesting site enters its critical section only after receiving all reply messages.
- Upon exiting the critical section, the site sends all deferred reply messages.

C. Quorum System

A quorum is a subset of nodes or processes. Although the nodes and processes resembles, based on the conventions in [6], the term node is specifically used when referring to the role of a process as a quorum member. A quorum system D , also referred to as a coterie, for a traditional mutual exclusion is a set of quorums satisfying the following properties:

- Intersection: $\forall P, Q \in D :: P \cap Q \neq \emptyset$.
- Minimality: $\forall P, Q \in D, : P \neq Q : P \not\subseteq Q$.

If a process enters its critical section only after it has successfully locked all nodes in some quorum, then the intersection property ensures that no two processes can execute their critical sections concurrently. The minimality property ensures that no process is required to lock more nodes than necessary to achieve mutual exclusion.

Initial local state for process P_i

- ✓ int seq_Number $_i = 0$;
- ✓ int replyCount $_i = 0$;
- ✓ array of Boolean , RD $_i[j] = 0, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
- ✓ int Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen $_i = 0$

InvMutEx: Process P_i executes the following to invoke mutual exclusion:

1. $Seq_Number_i = Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen_i + 1$
2. Make a REQUEST(R_i) message, where $R_i = (Seq_Number_i, i)$.

3. Send this REQUEST message to all the other processes.

4. $ReplyCount_i = 0$

5. $RD_i[k] = 0, \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$

RecReq: Process P_i receive message REQUEST(R_j), where $R_j = (SN_j, j)$, from process P_j :

1. If P_i is requesting then there are two cases.

✓ P_i 's REQUEST has a higher priority than P_j 's REQUEST.

- In this case, P_i sets $RD_i[j] = 1$ and

- $Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen_i = \max(Highest_Sequence_Number_Seen_i, SN_j)$.

✓ P_i 's REQUEST has a lower priority than P_j 's REQUEST. In this case, P_i sends a REPLY to P_j .

2. If P_i is not requesting then send a REPLY message to P_j .

RcvReply: Process P_i receives REPLY message from process P_j :

1. $ReplyCount_i = ReplyCount_i + 1$

2. If (CheckExecuteCS) then execute CS.

FinCS: Process P_i finishes executing CS:

1. Send REPLY to all processes P_k , such that $RD_i[k] = 1$.

CheckExecuteCS: if ($ReplyCount_i = N-1$) then return *true* else return *false*.

Fig. 1: Ricart-Agrawala Algorithm

For a node x , let B_x denote the set of processes from which x can receive requests for the critical section. We refer to B_x as the membership set of x . For a grid quorum system, for every

node x , $B_x = O(\sqrt{n})$

Some existing quorum-based algorithms for GME use a special type of quorum system called the group quorum system [6]. In a group quorum system, any two quorums belonging to the same group need not intersect, whereas quorums belonging to different groups must intersect. We do not use a group quorum system in this paper; instead, we employ a traditional quorum system. Hereafter, the phrase "quorum system" is used to refer to "traditional quorum system."

D. Maekawa's Algorithm

Maekawa's algorithm implements mutual exclusion by using a coterie that satisfies the aforementioned properties. Lamport's logical clock [2] is used to assign a time stamp to every request for a critical section. A request with a smaller time stamp has

a higher priority than a request with a larger time stamp (ties are broken using process identifiers). Maekawa's algorithm works as follows:

1. When a process wishes to enter a critical section, it selects a quorum and sends a REQUEST message to all the quorum members. It enters the critical section once it has successfully locked all its quorum members. On leaving the critical section, the process unlocks all its quorum members by sending a RELEASED message.
2. A node, on receiving a REQUEST message, checks to see whether it has already been locked by some other process. If not, it grants the lock to the requesting process by sending a LOCKED message to it. Otherwise, the node uses time stamps to determine whether the process currently holding a lock on it (hereafter referred to as the locking process) should be preempted. If the node decides not to preempt the locking process, it sends a FAILED message to the requesting process. Otherwise, it sends an INQUIRE message to the locking process.
3. A process, on receiving an INQUIRE message from a quorum member, unlocks the member by sending a RELINQUISH message as and when it realizes that it will not be able to successfully lock all its quorum members. This is ascertained when a FAILED message is received from one of the quorum members.
4. A node, on receiving a RELINQUISH or RELEASED message, grants the lock to the process whose request has the highest priority among all the pending requests, if any. Maekawa [16] proved that the message complexity of the above algorithm is $O(q)$, where q is the maximum size of a quorum. Further, its synchronization delay and waiting time are both two message hops. The synchronization delay is two message hops because once a process leaves the critical section, another process can enter the critical section after all the quorum members of the former process have received a RELEASED message and the latter process has received a LOCKED message from its quorum members. (When analyzing the synchronization delay of a quorum-based algorithm derived from Maekawa's algorithm, we ignore the delay incurred due to an exchange of deadlock avoidance messages. This is consistent with the practice of other researchers [16], [2].) Likewise, the waiting time is two message hops because if a process generates a request when there is no other request in the system, then the requesting process can enter the critical section within two message hops after all its quorum members have received its REQUEST message and it has received a LOCKED message from all its quorum members.

III. Proposed Algorithm

A. Procedure

As the process of the mutual exclusion, in the same manner processes request the coordinator to enter into the critical section, the coordinator checks with the applications requested by the processes and then based on the availability it responds which is the process of the existing system, in this paper we are proposing a new approach in which the process need not to wait to enter into the critical section.

When the process sends request to the coordinator, then the

coordinator checks with the application, then it duplicates the application and allots to the process.

The process will enter into the critical section without delay-time. The process will remain same for all the processes which want to access the same application.

When the process completed its access, it releases the application to the coordinator, and then the coordinator deletes the instance of the application when it is released.

In this way the coordinator allots the applications to the process without making them to wait for a long time to enter into critical section or to access the desired application.

The applications which are going to be allotting to the process by the coordinator/server those applications initially need to be deployed into the coordinator/server. The application should design in such a way which can be executed in the network environments.

B. Pre-requisite of the application

The application should develop on object oriented environments.

C. Terminology

Coordinator: It is a Server/ Operating system which is going to take care of all the issues related to thread/Application allocation to the process.

Process: The work of this is to access the properties (Applications) available at the server/operating system.

Application: It is a thread which is going to be executing under the process.

Algorithm

1. Coordinator accept the request form the process
2. Coordinator search the application requested by process under its environment.
3. If found, and then create the copy of application (Instance of the application).
4. The copy will be allotted to the requested process by the coordinator.
5. When the process release the applications to the coordinator, the coordinator will destroy the instance of the application allocated to the requested process.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper we proposed a new approach which overcomes the problem of delay-time to enter into critical section for the process. The coordinator should know how many instances of the applications are created when it is going to destroy, after that it should update the no of instances running presently.

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